

THE IMPORTANCE OF ORGANIC SEMICONDUCTORS TODAY

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Abstract. *Organic semiconductors have become a focal point of research and development due to their unique properties and versatile applications. These materials offer promising advancements in flexible electronics, organic light-emitting diodes (OLEDs), and organic photovoltaic cells. This article delves into the significance of organic semiconductors in today's technological landscape, examining their advantages, current applications, and future potential. Through a comprehensive review of the available literature and a detailed analysis of recent developments, the role of organic semiconductors is highlighted.*

Keywords: *organic semiconductors, flexible electronics, OLEDs, organic photovoltaics, materials science, electronic devices.*

Introduction. Organic semiconductors composed of carbon-based molecules are of great interest because of their potential for innovation in various technological fields. They mainly consist of carbon, hydrogen, oxygen, nitrogen and other nonmetals. They can be small organic molecules or large polymer chains. Unlike traditional inorganic semiconductors (silicon, germanium, etc.), organic semiconductors offer advantages such as mechanical flexibility, low manufacturing costs, and the ability to process at low temperatures. These attributes allow them to be used in a wide range of applications, from flexible displays to solar energy harvesting devices. This article explores the importance of organic semiconductors, highlighting their current uses and future prospects.

Literature review. The first studies of organic semiconductors began in the middle of the 20th century, and significant progress has been made in the last few decades. Research is primarily aimed at improving the electrical properties, stability and production technologies of these materials. In 2000, Heger, McDiarmid, and Shirakawa, who received the Nobel Prize in Chemistry, laid the foundation for modern advances in organic electronics [1]. Recent literature has reported significant advances in organic field-effect transistors, OLEDs, and organic photovoltaics, demonstrating their potential to compete with traditional silicon-based technologies [2,3].

Some differences between organic and inorganic semiconductors: Manufacturing technology for inorganic semiconductors often involves high-temperature processes such as epitaxy and photolithography, while organic semiconductors are fabricated using solution-based methods, that is, it can be processed at low temperatures.

Organic semiconductors can be produced at lower cost due to simpler processing techniques and the abundance of raw materials in nature, while offering advantages such as mechanical flexibility not found in conventional solid inorganic elements.

Health monitoring wearables often require flexibility to conform to the contours of the body. Flexible sensors made of organic semiconductors can easily monitor human vital signs.

Research Methodology. This article used the method of scientific analysis in terms of quality and quantity. Academic journals and patents were reviewed and studied to gather information on the development and applications of organic semiconductors. Key performance indicators in this field were analyzed to assess the prospects and challenges of the calculated electro-physical properties. In addition, expert interviews and case studies were used to gain insight into practical applications and future trends.

Figure 1. Molecular structure of some organic semiconductors: a, b, c and d - donor organic semiconductors; e, f, g and h are acceptor organic semiconductors [4].

Analysis and results. The analysis shows that organic semiconductors have made significant progress in various fields. In the field of mechanical flexible electronics, these materials enable the fabrication of flexible and wearable devices that are gaining popularity in consumer electronics. A key success story of organic semiconductors, OLED technology has revolutionized the display and lighting industry with superior color quality and energy efficiency.

Figure 2. Structure of a flexible OLED device. a) flexible plastic OLED device with metal electrodes can be built. b) Power generation diagram of the optimized OLED. c) Photo of flexible OLED above [5].

Figure 3 shows the increase in efficiency over the years, as a result of studies of various solar photovoltaics. It is worth noting that as a result of the research, the first organic solar cells were made in 2001, and organic tandem solar cells were made in 2008. Their efficiency is currently 19.2 and 14.2%, respectively [6].

Organic solar photovoltaics can be produced at low cost. That said, the potential for low-cost manufacturing through technologies such as roll-to-roll printing offers attractive economic benefits over traditional silicon solar cells that require more energy-intensive manufacturing processes.

As a result of current research, researchers are focusing on developing new organic compounds that can absorb a wider spectrum of sunlight and improve charge transport properties. Planning at a higher level than integrating organic solar materials with another technology such as perovskite solar energy or silicon photovoltaics to identify hybrid systems to maximize the efficiency of integration with other technology.

Despite these advances, some challenges remain, such as material stability, charge transport efficiency, and large-scale production. Recent studies show that combining new materials such as perovskites with organic semiconductors can solve some of these problems and lead to more robust and efficient devices [7,8].

Organic semiconductors offer advantages such as mechanical flexibility, lightweight properties and environmentally friendly properties, and the possibility of manufacturing from inexpensive materials.

Figure 3. The main elements that make up organic solar photovoltaics and research shows that the efficiency increases over the years [6].

Conclusions. Organic semiconductors have great potential to improve various fields through their unique properties and diverse properties. Much research and development is essential to overcome existing problems and unlock the full potential of these materials. Collaboration between academia, industry, and government agencies is critical to the development of innovation and commercialization of organic semiconductor technologies. Organic photovoltaic technology offers great opportunities for renewable energy production with its own advantages over traditional solar technologies. They are very important for new technologies in modern electronics and optoelectronics. Future research should focus on increasing material stability, improving manufacturing technology, and researching new hybrid materials to further advance this field. In Uzbekistan, investments are being made in various scientific areas, including scientific projects and research experiments on the physics of semiconductors and polymers. Increasing government support for such research and development will help the development of organic semiconductor technologies.

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